

Strongly 2-Multiplicative Graphs

D.D.Somashekara[†], C.R.Veena[‡] and H.E.Ravi[†]

[†]. Department of Studies in Mathematics, University of Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore-570006, India

[‡]. Department of Mathematics, JSS College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Mysore-570025, India

E-mail: dsomashekara@yahoo.com, veenacr.maths@gmail.com ravihemath64@gmail.com

Abstract: Since the year 2000 a number of authors have studied strongly multiplicative graphs. In this vein we introduce the concept of strongly k -multiplicative graph and prove that certain class of graphs such as paths, binary tree, cycle etc. are strongly 2-multiplicative.

Key Words: Strongly 2-multiplicative, graph labelling, paths, star, fan graph, binary tree, comb graph, triangular snake, ladder.

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§1. Introduction

A graph G consists of a nonempty set $V = V(G)$ of points called vertices and another set $E = E(G)$ whose elements are called edges where each edge is identified with an unordered pair of vertices in V . Each pair $e = (u, v)$ in E of points of V is an edge of G and is said to be incident with u and v . In this case u and v are said to be adjacent to each other. The number of vertices in G is called the order of G .

We begin with some basic definitions and notations [7], [12], [6].

Definition 1.1 A walk of a graph G is a finite, alternative sequence of vertices and edges $v_0, e_1, v_1, e_2, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}, e_n, v_n$, beginning with v_0 and ending with v_n such that each edge e_i is incident with v_{i-1} and v_i . The number of edges is called the length of the walk. A walk is called a path if all its vertices (and thus necessarily all the edges) are distinct. A path on n vertices is denoted by P_n .

Definition 1.2 A walk in a graph is closed if its initial and terminal vertices are identical. A closed walk is called a cycle. A cycle on $n(\geq 3)$ vertices is denoted by C_n .

Definition 1.3 A graph G is said to be complete if every pair of its distinct vertices are adjacent. A complete graph on n vertices is denoted by K_n .

Definition 1.4 A bigraph or bipartite graph is a graph whose vertex set $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two subsets V_1 and V_2 such that every edge of G joins a vertex of V_1 with a vertex of V_2 . (V_1, V_2) is a bipartition of G .

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A complete bipartite graph is a bipartite graph with bipartition (V_1, V_2) such that every vertex of V_1 is joined to all the vertices of V_2 . If V_1 contains m points and V_2 contains n points then the complete bipartite graph is denoted by $K_{m,n}$. A star $K_{1,n}$ is a complete bipartite graph.

Definition 1.5 A graph is acyclic if it has no cycles. A tree is a connected acyclic graph.

Definition 1.6 The wheel W_n ($n \geq 4$) is the graph obtained from the join of K_1 and C_{n-1} .

Definition 1.7 A fan F_n ($n \geq 2$) is the graph obtained from the join of the path P_n and K_1 .

Definition 1.8 A ladder L_n is a graph with vertex set $V(L_n) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\}$ and edge set $E(L_n) = \{v_{2i}v_{2i+2}, v_{2i-1}v_{2i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_{2i-1}v_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$.

Definition 1.9 A triangular ladder is a graph T_n , whose vertex set is $V(T_n) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\}$ and whose edge set is $E(T_n) = E(L_n) \cup \{v_{2i}v_{2i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$.

Definition 1.10 A complete n -ary tree is a tree in which every internal vertex is of degree $n+1$, the root vertex is of degree n and the pendent vertices are of degree 1 and have the same depth.

Definition 1.11 A chord of a cycle C_n is an edge joining two non-adjacent vertices of the cycle C_n .

Definition 1.12 The graph obtained by joining a single pendent edge to each vertex of a path is called a comb.

Definition 1.13 Duplication of a vertex v by a new edge $e = uv$ in a graph G produces a new graph G' such that $N(u) = \{v, w\}$ and $N(w) = \{u, v\}$.

Definition 1.14 Duplication of an edge $e = uv$ by a new vertex w in a graph G produces a new graph G' such that $N(w) = \{u, v\}$.

Definition 1.15 A triangular snake is a graph obtained from the duplication of each edge of a path by a new vertex.

Definition 1.16 The windmill graph K_n^m , ($n > 3$) consists of m copies of K_n with a vertex in common.

Consider a graph G of order n . Let P_1 and P_2 be two paths in G with the same vertex set V . Then we say that P_1 and P_2 are path homotopic with respect to V . We denote this by $P_1 \simeq_V P_2$. One can easily prove that this relation is an equivalence relation. Let \mathcal{P} be the path homotopy class consisting of those paths which are path homotopic to the path P with a given vertex set and let \mathcal{A} denote the set of all distinct path homotopy classes in G .

Definition 1.17 A graph G of order n is said to be strongly k -multiplicative if there is an injective mapping $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ such that the induced mapping $h : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ defined by $h(\mathcal{P}) = \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} f(v_{j_i})$, where $j_1, j_2, \dots, j_{k+1} \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $k+1 \leq n$ and \mathcal{P} is the path

homotopy class of paths having the vertex set $\{v_{j_1}, v_{j_2}, \dots, v_{j_{k+1}}\}$, is injective.

In particular, if $k=2$ we call G , strongly 2- multiplicative and if $k=1$, then we call G , strongly 1- multiplicative or simply strongly multiplicative.

In 2001, L. W. Beineke and S. M. Hegde [5] have introduced the concept of strongly multiplicative graphs. Since then many authors including C. Adiga, H. N. Ramaswamy and D. D. Somashekara [2],[3], [4], M. A. Seoud and A. Zid [9], B. D. Acharya, Germina and Ajitha [1], S. K. Vaidya and K. K. Kanani [10], [11] and M. Muthusamy, K. C. Raajasekar and J. Basker Babujee [8] have also studied and contributed to the concept of strongly multiplicative graphs. For more details one may refer the survey article “A dynamic survey of graph labeling” by J. A. Gallian [6].

In the next section we prove our main results.

§2. Main Results

We first note that for a graph to be strongly 2-multiplicative, it has to have at least 3 vertices.

Theorem 2.1 *The path P_n is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider a path P_n of length $n - 1$. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$ for all i . Then \mathcal{A} consists of $n - 2$ distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_{n-2}$, where \mathcal{P}_i is the path homotopy class of paths having the vertex set $\{v_i, v_{i+1}, v_{i+2}\}$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_i) = (i)(i + 1)(i + 2)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$. Since $i(i + 1)(i + 2) < (i + 1)(i + 2)(i + 3)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 3$, it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_i) < h(\mathcal{P}_{i+1})$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 3$. Hence h is injective and P_n is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.2 *Every cycle C_n , is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider a cycle $C_n = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, v_1)$ of order n and let p be the largest prime less than n . We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for $1 \leq i \leq p - 1$, $v_i = i + 1$, for $p \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $v_n = p$. If $n = 3$, then \mathcal{A} consists of only one path homotopy class and is trivially strongly 2-multiplicative. If $n > 3$, then \mathcal{A} consists of n distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n$, where \mathcal{P}_i is the path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_i, v_{i+1}, v_{i+2}\}$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$, \mathcal{P}_{n-1} is the path homotopy class of paths having the vertex set $\{v_{n-1}, v_n, v_1\}$ and \mathcal{P}_n is the path homotopy class of paths having the vertex set $\{v_n, v_1, v_2\}$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_i) = (i)(i + 1)(i + 2)$, for $1 \leq i \leq p - 3$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{p-2}) = (p - 2)(p - 1)(p + 1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{p-1}) = (p - 1)(p + 1)(p + 2)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_i) = (i + 1)(i + 2)(i + 3)$, for $p \leq i \leq n - 3$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n - 1)(n)(p)$ or $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n - 2)(n)(p)$, if p is the immediate predecessor of n , $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) = n \cdot p \cdot 1$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_n) = p \cdot 1 \cdot 2$. Then from the definition of h it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_i) < h(\mathcal{P}_{i+1})$, $1 \leq i \leq n - 3$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_n) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2})$, also $h(\mathcal{P}_i) \neq h(\mathcal{P}_j)$, $n - 2 \leq j \leq n$ and $1 \leq i \leq n - 3$. Since $h(\mathcal{P}_j)$ is divisible by p , where as $h(\mathcal{P}_i)$ is not, h is injective and the graph C_n is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.3 *Every cycle with one chord is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof First, consider a cycle C_4 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 . Let the chord be $e = v_1v_3$. We label the vertices as follows: $v_1 = 1, v_2 = 4, v_3 = 2$ and $v_4 = 3$. Then \mathcal{A} consists of 4 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3$ and \mathcal{P}_4 , corresponding to the path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4, v_1\}$ and $\{v_4, v_1, v_2\}$ respectively. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12$. Clearly h is injective and C_4 with one chord is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Second, consider a cycle C_5 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 . Let the chord be $e = v_1v_3$. We label the vertices as follows: $v_1 = 1, v_2 = 4, v_3 = 2, v_4 = 5$ and $v_5 = 3$. Then \mathcal{A} consists of 7 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6$ and \mathcal{P}_7 , corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_5, v_1\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_2\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_3\}$ and $\{v_4, v_3, v_1\}$ respectively. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1)=8, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 30, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 15, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 6$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 10$. Clearly h is injective and C_5 with one chord is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, let $n > 5$. Consider a cycle $C_n = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, v_1)$ of order n and let p_1 and p_2 be the two consecutive primes such that $0 < p_2 < p_1 < n$ and that p_1 is the largest. Let $e = v_1v_{p_2}$ be the chord of the cycle C_n . We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for $1 \leq i \leq p_1 - 1$, $v_i = i + 1$, for $p_1 \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $v_n = p_1$. Then \mathcal{A} consists of $n + 4$ ($n + 2$, in case $n = 6$ and $n = 7$) distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n, \mathcal{P}_{n+1}, \mathcal{P}_{n+2}, \mathcal{P}_{n+3}, \mathcal{P}_{n+4}$, where \mathcal{P}_i is the path homotopy class of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_i, v_{i+1}, v_{i+2}\}$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$ and $\mathcal{P}_{n-1}, \mathcal{P}_n, \mathcal{P}_{n+1}, \mathcal{P}_{n+2}, \mathcal{P}_{n+3}$ and \mathcal{P}_{n+4} are the path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex set $\{v_{n-1}, v_n, v_1\}, \{v_n, v_1, v_2\}, \{v_n, v_1, v_{p_2}\}, \{v_{p_2+1}, v_{p_2}, v_1\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_{p_2}\}$ and $\{v_{p_2-1}, v_{p_2}, v_1\}$ respectively. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_i) = (i)(i+1)(i+2)$, for $1 \leq i \leq p_1 - 3$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{p_1-2}) = (p_1 - 2)(p_1 - 1)(p_1 + 1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{p_1-1}) = (p_1 - 1)(p_1 + 1)(p_1 + 2)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_i) = (i + 1)(i + 2)(i + 3)$, for $p_1 \leq i \leq n - 3$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n - 1)(n)(p_1)$ or $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n - 2)(n)(p_1)$, if p_1 is the immediate predecessor of n , $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) = n.p_1.1$, $h(\mathcal{P}_n) = p_1.1.2$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+1}) = p_1.1.p_2$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+2}) = (p_2 + 1).p_2.1$ $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+3}) = 2.1.p_2$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+4}) = (p_2 - 1).p_2.1$. Then from the definition of h it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_i) < h(\mathcal{P}_{i+1})$, for $1 \leq i \leq p_2 - 3$ and $p_2 + 1 \leq i \leq n - 3$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_n) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2})$, also $h(\mathcal{P}_i) \neq h(\mathcal{P}_j)$, $1 \leq i \leq p_2 - 3$, $p_2 + 1 \leq i \leq n - 3$ and $n - 2 \leq j \leq n$. Since $h(\mathcal{P}_j)$ is divisible by p_1 , whereas $h(\mathcal{P}_i)$ is not. $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+3}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+4}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+2}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{p_2-2}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{p_2-1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{p_2})$ and these are not equal to $h(\mathcal{P}_i)$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_j)$, where $1 \leq i \leq p_2 - 3$, $p_2 + 1 \leq i \leq n - 3$ and $n - 2 \leq j \leq n$, since these are divisible by p_2 whereas $h(\mathcal{P}_i)$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_j)$ are not. Hence h is injective and $C_n, n > 5$ with one chord is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Remark 2.4 (1) In general, a cycle $C_n = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, v_1)$ with one chord joining any two non adjacent vertices, can be shown to be strongly 2-multiplicative.

(2) A cycle with twin chords can be shown to be strongly 2-multiplicative.

Theorem 2.5 *The graph obtained by duplication of an arbitrary vertex of a cycle by a new edge is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider a cycle $C_n = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, v_1)$. We duplicate the vertex v_n by an edge e with end vertices v_{n+1} and v_{n+2} . Let the graph so obtained be G . Then $|V(G)| = n + 2$ and $|E(G)| = n + 3$. Let p be the largest prime less than n . We label the vertices as

follows: $v_i=i$, for $1 \leq i \leq p-1$ and for $n < i \leq n+2$, $v_i = i+1$, for $p \leq i \leq n-1$ and $v_n = p$. If $n = 3$, then \mathcal{A} consists of 6 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5$ and \mathcal{P}_6 , corresponding to the path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$, $\{v_3, v_4, v_5\}$, $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, $\{v_2, v_3, v_5\}$, $\{v_1, v_3, v_4\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, v_5\}$ respectively. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 10$. If $n > 3$, then \mathcal{A} consists of $n+5$ distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n, \mathcal{P}_{n+1}, \mathcal{P}_{n+2}, \mathcal{P}_{n+3}, \mathcal{P}_{n+4}, \mathcal{P}_{n+5}$, where \mathcal{P}_i is the path homotopy class of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_i, v_{i+1}, v_{i+2}\}$, for $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ and $\mathcal{P}_{n-1}, \mathcal{P}_n, \mathcal{P}_{n+1}, \mathcal{P}_{n+2}, \mathcal{P}_{n+3}, \mathcal{P}_{n+4}$ and \mathcal{P}_{n+5} are the path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_{n-1}, v_n, v_1\}$, $\{v_n, v_1, v_2\}$, $\{v_n, v_{n+1}, v_{n+2}\}$, $\{v_{n+1}, v_n, v_{n-1}\}$, $\{v_{n+1}, v_n, v_1\}$, $\{v_{n+2}, v_n, v_{n-1}\}$ and $\{v_{n+2}, v_n, v_1\}$ respectively. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_i) = (i)(i+1)(i+2)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n-3$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n-2)(n-1)(n+1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) = (n-1)(n+1)(n+2)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_n) = (n+1)(n+2)(n+3)$, for $p \leq i \leq n-3$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n-1)(n)(p)$ or $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) = (n-2)(n)(p)$, if p is the immediate predecessor of n , $h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) = n \cdot p \cdot 1$, $h(\mathcal{P}_n) = p \cdot 1 \cdot 2$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+1}) = p \cdot (n+1) \cdot (n+2)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+2}) = n \cdot p \cdot (n+1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+3}) = (n+1) \cdot p \cdot 1$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+4}) = (n+2) \cdot p \cdot n$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+5}) = (n+2) \cdot p \cdot 1$. Then from the definition of h it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_i) < h(\mathcal{P}_{i+1})$, $1 \leq i \leq n-3$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_n) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n-1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+3}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+5}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n-2}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+2}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+4}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{n+1})$ and these not equal to $h(\mathcal{P}_k)$ where $1 \leq k \leq n-3$, since these are divisible by p whereas $h(\mathcal{P}_k)$ is not. Hence h is injective and the graph obtained by duplication of an arbitrary vertex of a cycle by a new edge is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Remark 2.6 If we duplicate an edge in a cycle of an order n by a new vertex, then we obtain a cycle of order $n+1$ with one chord. Hence by Theorem 2.3 the graph obtained by duplication of an arbitrary edge of cycle by a new vertex is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Theorem 2.7 *The comb graph is strongly 2-multiplicative*

Proof Consider the comb graph G of order $2n(n \geq 2)$ with vertex set $G = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{2n}\}$ as shown below.

Figure 1

Then \mathcal{A} consists of $3n-4$ distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_{2i-1, 2i+1, 2i+3}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i-1, 2i, 2i+1}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i-1, 2i+1, 2i+2}$, corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having vertex sets $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+3}\}$, $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i}, v_{2i+1}\}$ and $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+2}\}$ respectively, for $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ and path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_{2n-3, 2n-2, 2n-1}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2n-3, 2n-1, 2n}$ corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_{2n-3}, v_{2n-2}, v_{2n-1}\}$ and $\{v_{2n-3}, v_{2n-1}, v_{2n}\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for all i . Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{i,j,k}) = i \cdot j \cdot k$. Since $(2i-1) \cdot (2i) \cdot (2i+1) < (2i-1) \cdot (2i+1) \cdot (2i+2) < (2i-1) \cdot$

$(2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 3)$, $(2i - 1) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 3) < (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 2) \cdot (2i + 3)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$ and $(2i - 1) \cdot (2i) \cdot (2i + 1) < (2i - 1) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 2)$ for $i = n - 1$, it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_{1,2,3}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{1,3,4}) < \dots < h(\mathcal{P}_{2n-3,2n-1,2n})$. Therefore h is injective and the comb graph is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.8 *The triangular snake graph is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider the triangular snake graph $T_n (n \geq 2)$ with vertex set $V(T_n) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{2n-1}\}$ as shown below.

Figure 2

Then \mathcal{A} consists of $5n - 9$ distinct path homotopy classes

$$\mathcal{P}_{2i-1,2i,2i+1}, \mathcal{P}_{2i-1,2i+1,2i+2}, \mathcal{P}_{2i-1,2i+1,2i+3}, \mathcal{P}_{2i,2i+1,2i+2}, \mathcal{P}_{2i,2i+1,2i+3}$$

corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having vertex sets

$$\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i}, v_{2i+1}\}, \{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+2}\}, \{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+3}\}, \{v_{2i}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+2}\}$$

and $\{v_{2i}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+3}\}$ respectively, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$ and path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_{2n-3,2n-2,2n-1}$ corresponding to path homotopy class of paths having the vertex set $\{v_{2n-3}, v_{2n-2}, v_{2n-1}\}$. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for all i . Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{i,j,k}) = i \cdot j \cdot k$. Since $(2i - 1) \cdot (2i) \cdot (2i + 1) < (2i - 1) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 2) < (2i - 1) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 3) < (2i) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 2) < (2i) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 3)$, $(2i) \cdot (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 3) < (2i + 1) \cdot (2i + 2) \cdot (2i + 3)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$ and $(2n - 3) \cdot (2n - 1) \cdot (2n - 4) < (2n - 3) \cdot (2n - 2) \cdot (2n - 1)$ it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_{1,2,3}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{1,3,4}) < \dots < h(\mathcal{P}_{2n-3,2n-2,2n-1})$. Therefore h is injective and the triangular snake graph is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.9 *The ladder graph L_n is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider the ladder graph L_n with vertex set $V(L_n) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{2n}\}$ as shown below.

Figure 3

Then \mathcal{A} consists of $6n - 8$ distinct path homotopy classes

$\mathcal{P}_{2i,2i-1,2i+1}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i-1,2i,2i+2}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i-1,2i+1,2i+2}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i-1,2i+1,2i+3}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i,2i+2,2i+4}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2i,2i+2,2i+1}$,
 corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having vertex sets $\{v_{2i}, v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}\}$, $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i}, v_{2i+2}\}$, $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+2}\}$, $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i+1}, v_{2i+3}\}$, $\{v_{2i}, v_{2i+2}, v_{2i+4}\}$ and $\{v_{2i}, v_{2i+2}, v_{2i+1}\}$ respectively, for $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ and path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_{2n-2,2n-3,2n-1}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2n-3,2n-2,2n}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2n-3,2n-1,2n}$, $\mathcal{P}_{2n-2,2n,2n-1}$ corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having the vertex sets $\{v_{2n-2}, v_{2n-3}, v_{2n-1}\}$, $\{v_{2n-3}, v_{2n-2}, v_{2n}\}$, $\{v_{2n-3}, v_{2n-1}, v_{2n}\}$ and $\{v_{2n-2}, v_{2n}, v_{2n-1}\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i=i$, for all i . Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{i,j,k}) = i \cdot j \cdot k$. Since $(2i) \cdot (2i-1) \cdot (2i+1) < (2i-1) \cdot (2i) \cdot (2i+2) < (2i-1) \cdot (2i+1) \cdot (2i+2) < (2i-1) \cdot (2i+1) \cdot (2i+3) < (2i) \cdot (2i+2) \cdot (2i+1) < (2i) \cdot (2i+2) \cdot (2i+4)$, $(2i) \cdot (2i+2) \cdot (2i+4) < (2i+2) \cdot (2i+1) \cdot (2i+3)$, for $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ and $(2i) \cdot (2i-1) \cdot (2i+1) < (2i-1) \cdot (2i) \cdot (2i+2) < (2i-1) \cdot (2i+1) \cdot (2i+2) < (2i) \cdot (2i+2) \cdot (2i+1)$ for $i = n-1$ it follows that $h(\mathcal{P}_{2,1,3}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{1,2,4}) < \dots < h(\mathcal{P}_{2n-2,2n,2n-1})$. Therefore h is injective and the graph L_n is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.10 *The binary tree is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider the binary tree G consisting of $2^{n+1} - 1$ vertices with n levels. We label the vertices, using breadth-first search method as follows $v_i = i$, for $1 \leq i \leq 2^{n+1} - 1$ as shown in the figure.

Figure 4

If $n = 1$ then the tree becomes a path with 3 vertices and is trivially strongly 2-multiplicative. So, let $n > 1$. Then for each m , consisting of the edges of level $m-1$ and of the level m , $1 < m \leq n-1$, there are $5 \cdot 2^{m-2}$ distinct path homotopy classes consisting of 2^{m-2} bunches of 5 path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_{m,r,1}$, $\mathcal{P}_{m,r,2}$, $\mathcal{P}_{m,r,3}$, $\mathcal{P}_{m,r,4}$, $\mathcal{P}_{m,r,5}$ corresponding to path homotopy classes of paths having vertex sets

$$\{v_{2^{m-2}+r-1}, v_{2(2^{m-2}+r-1)}, v_{2(2^{m-2}+r-1)+1}\}, \{v_{2^{m-2}+r-1}, v_{2(2^{m-2}+r-1)}, v_{4(2^{m-2}+r-1)}\},$$

$$\{v_{2^{m-2}+r-1}, v_{2(2^{m-2}+r-1)}, v_{4(2^{m-2}+r-1)+1}\}, \{v_{2^{m-2}+r-1}, v_{2(2^{m-2}+r-1)+1}, v_{4(2^{m-2}+r-1)+2}\}$$

and $\{v_{2^{m-2}+r-1}, v_{2(2^{m-2}+r-1)+1}, v_{4(2^{m-2}+r-1)+3}\}$ respectively, where $1 \leq r \leq 2^{m-2}$ and if $m = n$, in addition to $5 \cdot 2^{m-2}$ distinct path homotopy classes described above we have 2^{n-1} distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_{n+1,r,1}$ corresponding to the paths having vertex sets

$\{v_{2^{n-1}+r-1}, v_{2(2^{n-1}+r-1)}, v_{2(2^{n-1}+r-1)+1}\}$, where $1 \leq r \leq 2^{n-1}$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,1}) = (2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1)) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,2}) = (2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1)) \cdot (4(2^{m-2} + r - 1))$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,3}) = (2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1)) \cdot (4(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,4}) = (2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 1) \cdot (4(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 2)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,5}) = (2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 1) \cdot (4(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 3)$, for $1 < m \leq n$, $1 \leq r \leq 2^{m-2}$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_{n+1,r,1}) = (2^{n-1} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{n-1} + r - 1)) \cdot (2(2^{n-1} + r - 1) + 1)$, for $1 \leq r \leq 2^{n-1}$. Then to show h is injective, consider the following cases:

Case 1. Let $k = 2^{m-2} + r - 1$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,2}) = k \cdot 2k \cdot 4k$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,3}) = k \cdot 2k \cdot (4k + 1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,4}) = k \cdot (2k + 1) \cdot (4k + 2)$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,5}) = k \cdot (2k + 1) \cdot (4k + 3)$. Since $2k < 2k + 1$ and $4k < 4k + 1 < 4k + 2 < 4k + 3$, we have $k \cdot 2k \cdot 4k < k \cdot 2k \cdot (4k + 1) < k \cdot (2k + 1) \cdot (4k + 2) < k \cdot (2k + 1) \cdot (4k + 3)$. Hence $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,2}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,3}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,4}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,5})$.

Case 2. Let $k = 2^{m-1} - 1$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,2^{m-2},5}) = k \cdot (2k + 1) \cdot (4k + 3)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m+1,1,2}) = (k + 1) \cdot (2(k + 1)) \cdot (4(k + 1))$. Since $k < k + 1$, $2k + 1 < 2k + 2$ and $4k + 3 < 4k + 4$, we have $k \cdot 2k + 1 \cdot 4k + 3 < k + 1 \cdot 2k + 2 \cdot 4k + 4$. Hence $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,2^{m-2},5}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m+1,1,2})$.

Case 3. Let $k = 2^{m-2} + r - 1$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,5}) = k \cdot (2k + 1) \cdot (4k + 3)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r+1,1}) = (k + 1) \cdot (2(k + 1)) \cdot (4(k + 1))$. Since $k < k + 1$, $2k + 1 < 2k + 2$ and $4k + 3 < 4k + 4$, we have $k \cdot 2k + 1 \cdot 4k + 3 < k + 1 \cdot 2k + 2 \cdot 4k + 4$. Hence $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,5}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r+1,1})$, for $1 \leq r \leq 2^{m-2} - 1$.

Case 4. Since $r - 1 < r$, we have $(2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1)) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 1) < ((2^{m-2}) + r) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r)) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r) + 1)$, which is same as $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r+1,1})$, for $1 \leq r \leq 2^{m-2} - 1$.

Case 5. Let $k = 2^{m-1} - 1$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,2^{m-2},1}) = k \cdot 2k \cdot (2k + 1)$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{m+1,1,1}) = (k + 1) \cdot (2(k + 1)) \cdot (2(k + 1) + 1)$. Since $k < k + 1$, $2k < 2k + 2$ and $2k + 1 < 2k + 3$, we have $k \cdot 2k \cdot (2k + 1) < (k + 1) \cdot (2k + 2) \cdot (2k + 3)$. Hence $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,2^{m-2},1}) < h(\mathcal{P}_{m+1,1,1})$.

Case 6. For given m and r , we have $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,1}) = (2^{m-2} + r - 1) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1)) \cdot (2(2^{m-2} + r - 1) + 1)$ in which one of the three factors differs from the three factors of $h(\mathcal{P}_{s,t,i})$ for $s < m$, $1 \leq t \leq 2^{s-1}$, $1 \leq i \leq 5$ and for $s = m$, $1 \leq t < r \leq 2^{m-2}$, $1 \leq i \leq 5$. Hence $h(\mathcal{P}_{m,r,1}) \neq h(\mathcal{P}_{s,t,i})$ for $s < m$, $1 \leq t \leq 2^{s-1}$, $1 \leq i \leq 5$ and for $s = m$, $1 \leq t < r \leq 2^{m-2}$, $1 \leq i \leq 5$.

Thus, by Cases (1)-(6) it follows that h is injective and G is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.11 *The complete graph K_n is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $3 \leq n \leq 5$.*

Proof First, consider K_3 with vertices v_1, v_2 and v_3 . Then there is only one path homotopy class and is trivially strongly 2-multiplicative.

Second, consider K_4 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3 and v_4 . Then there are four distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3$ and \mathcal{P}_4 , corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$, $\{v_1, v_2, v_4\}$, $\{v_1, v_3, v_4\}$ and $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i$, $1 \leq i \leq 4$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 24$. Clearly h is injective and K_4 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Third, consider K_5 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 and v_5 . Then there are ten distinct path

homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9$ and \mathcal{P}_{10} , corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}, \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_1, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_5, v_1\}, \{v_3, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_5, v_1\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_2\}$ and $\{v_5, v_2, v_3\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i=i, 1 \leq i \leq 5$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 20, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 60, h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 15, h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 8$ and $h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 30$. Clearly h is injective and K_5 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider a complete graph K_n , where $n \geq 6$. Clearly corresponding to each triangle, one can always find a path homotopy class of paths of length 2 having the vertex set, the vertices of triangle. In any labelling of the vertices, we can find two path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' where \mathcal{P} consisting of paths having the vertices labelled 1, 3 and 4 and \mathcal{P}' consisting of paths having the vertices labelled 1, 2 and 6. Clearly $\mathcal{P} \neq \mathcal{P}'$, but $h(\mathcal{P}) = 12 = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence for $n \geq 6, K_n$ is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.12 *The star graph S_n is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $3 \leq n \leq 7$.*

Proof First, consider S_3 with vertices v_1, v_2 and v_3 . Here v_2, v_3 are pendent vertices. Then there is only one path homotopy class and is trivially strongly 2-multiplicative.

Second, consider S_4 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3 and v_4 . Here v_2, v_3, v_4 are pendent vertices. Then there are three distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2$ and \mathcal{P}_3 , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}$ and $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i, 1 \leq i \leq 4$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 12$. Clearly h is injective and S_4 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Third, consider S_5 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 and v_5 . Here v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 are pendent vertices. Then there are six distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5$ and \mathcal{P}_6 , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}$ and $\{v_4, v_1, v_5\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i, 1 \leq i \leq 5$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 15, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 20$. Clearly h is injective and S_5 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Fourth, consider S_6 with vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 and v_6 . Here v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 are pendent vertices. Then there are ten distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9$ and \mathcal{P}_{10} , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_6\}$ and $\{v_5, v_1, v_6\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_1 = 2, v_2 = 1, v_i = i, 3 \leq i \leq 6$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 30, h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 36, h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 48, h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 60$. Clearly h is injective and S_6 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Fifth, consider S_7 with vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6$ and v_7 . Here $v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7$ are pendent vertices. Then there are fifteen distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9, \mathcal{P}_{10}, \mathcal{P}_{11}, \mathcal{P}_{12}, \mathcal{P}_{13}, \mathcal{P}_{14}$ and \mathcal{P}_{15} , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_7\}$ and $\{v_6, v_1, v_7\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_1=2, v_2 = 1, v_i=i, 3 \leq i \leq 7$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 14, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 30, h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 36, h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 42, h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 48, h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 56, h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 60, h(\mathcal{P}_{14}) = 70,$

$h(\mathcal{P}_{15}) = 84$. Clearly h is injective and S_7 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider a star graph S_n , where $n \geq 8$. In any labeling of the vertices we can find two path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' such that $\mathcal{P} \neq \mathcal{P}'$ but $h(\mathcal{P}) = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence for $n \geq 8$, S_n is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.13 *The fan graph F_n is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $3 \leq n \leq 6$.*

Proof First, consider $F_2 = K_1 + P_2$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of P_2 be v_2 and v_3 . Then there is only one path homotopy class and is trivially strongly 2-multiplicative.

Second, consider $F_3 = K_1 + P_3$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of P_3 be v_2, v_3 and v_4 . Then there are four distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3$ and \mathcal{P}_4 , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}$ and $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i$, $1 \leq i \leq 4$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 24$. Clearly h is injective and F_3 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Third, consider $F_4 = K_1 + P_4$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of P_4 be v_2, v_3, v_4 and v_5 . Then there are eight distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7$ and \mathcal{P}_8 , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_4, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ and $\{v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i$, $1 \leq i \leq 5$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 10$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 15$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 20$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 60$. Clearly h is injective and F_4 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Fourth, consider $F_5 = K_1 + P_5$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of P_5 be v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 and v_6 . Then there are thirteen distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9, \mathcal{P}_{10}, \mathcal{P}_{11}, \mathcal{P}_{12}$ and \mathcal{P}_{13} , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_4, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_4, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_5, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, $\{v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ and $\{v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_1 = 3$, $v_i = i - 1$, $i = 2, 3$, $v_i = i$, $4 \leq i \leq 6$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 15$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 18$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 36$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 60$, $h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 72$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 90$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 120$. Clearly h is injective and F_5 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Fifth, consider $F_6 = K_1 + P_6$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of P_6 be v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 and v_7 . Then there are nineteen distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9, \mathcal{P}_{10}, \mathcal{P}_{11}, \mathcal{P}_{12}, \mathcal{P}_{13}, \mathcal{P}_{14}, \mathcal{P}_{15}, \mathcal{P}_{16}, \mathcal{P}_{17}, \mathcal{P}_{18}$ and \mathcal{P}_{19} , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_2, v_1, v_7\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_3, v_1, v_7\}$, $\{v_4, v_1, v_5\}$, $\{v_4, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_4, v_1, v_7\}$, $\{v_5, v_1, v_6\}$, $\{v_5, v_1, v_7\}$, $\{v_6, v_1, v_7\}$, $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, $\{v_3, v_4, v_5\}$, $\{v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ and $\{v_5, v_6, v_7\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_1 = 3$, $v_i = i - 1$, $i = 2, 3$, $v_i = i$, $4 \leq i \leq 7$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 15$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 18$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 21$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 36$, $h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 42$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 60$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 72$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 84$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 90$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{14}) = 105$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{15}) = 126$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{16}) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{17}) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{18}) = 120$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{19}) = 210$. Clearly h is injective and F_6 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider a fan graph F_n , where $n \geq 7$. In any labeling of the vertices we can find two path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' such that $\mathcal{P} \neq \mathcal{P}'$ but $h(\mathcal{P}) = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence for $n \geq 7$, F_n is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.14 *The wheel graph W_n is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $4 \leq n \leq 7$.*

Proof First, consider $W_4 = K_1 + C_3$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of C_3 be v_2, v_3 and v_4 . Then there are four distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3$ and \mathcal{P}_4 corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}$ and $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i, 1 \leq i \leq 4$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 24$. Clearly h is injective and W_4 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Second, consider $W_5 = K_1 + C_4$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of C_4 be v_2, v_3, v_4 and v_5 . Then there are ten distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9$ and \mathcal{P}_{10} corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_5, v_2\}$ and $\{v_5, v_2, v_3\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_i = i, 1 \leq i \leq 5$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 15, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 20, h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 60, h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 30$. Clearly h is injective and W_5 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Third, consider $W_6 = K_1 + C_5$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of C_5 be v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 and v_6 . Then there are fifteen distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9, \mathcal{P}_{10}, \mathcal{P}_{11}, \mathcal{P}_{12}, \mathcal{P}_{13}, \mathcal{P}_{14}$ and \mathcal{P}_{15} corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_5, v_6\}, \{v_5, v_6, v_2\}$ and $\{v_6, v_2, v_3\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_1 = 2, v_2 = 1, v_3 = 3, v_4 = 6, v_5 = 4, v_6 = 5$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 36, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 30, h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 48, h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 60, h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 18, h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 72, h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 120, h(\mathcal{P}_{14}) = 20, h(\mathcal{P}_{15}) = 15$. Clearly h is injective and W_6 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Fourth, consider $W_7 = K_1 + C_6$. Let the vertex of K_1 be v_1 and the vertices of C_6 be v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 and v_7 . Then there are twenty one distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9, \mathcal{P}_{10}, \mathcal{P}_{11}, \mathcal{P}_{12}, \mathcal{P}_{13}, \mathcal{P}_{14}, \mathcal{P}_{15}, \mathcal{P}_{16}, \mathcal{P}_{17}, \mathcal{P}_{18}, \mathcal{P}_{19}, \mathcal{P}_{20}$ and \mathcal{P}_{21} , corresponding to paths having the vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_6, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_5, v_6\}, \{v_5, v_6, v_7\}, \{v_6, v_7, v_2\}$ and $\{v_7, v_2, v_3\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows : $v_1 = 2, v_2 = 1, v_i = i, \text{ for } i = 3, 7, v_4 = 6, v_5 = 4, v_6 = 5$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6, h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 12, h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 8, h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 10, h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 14, h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 36, h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 24, h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 30, h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 42, h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 48, h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 60, h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 84, h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 40, h(\mathcal{P}_{14}) = 56, h(\mathcal{P}_{15}) = 70, h(\mathcal{P}_{16}) = 18, h(\mathcal{P}_{17}) = 72, h(\mathcal{P}_{18}) = 120, h(\mathcal{P}_{19}) = 140, h(\mathcal{P}_{20}) = 35, h(\mathcal{P}_{21}) = 21$. Clearly h is injective and W_7 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider a wheel graph W_n , where $n \geq 8$. In any labeling of the vertices we can find two path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' such that $\mathcal{P} \neq \mathcal{P}'$ but $h(\mathcal{P}) = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence for $n \geq 8, W_n$ is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.15 *The complete bipartite graph $K_{2,n}$ is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $2 \leq n \leq 3$.*

Proof First, consider complete bipartite graph $K_{2,2}$. Let $A = \{v_1, v_2\}$ and $B = \{v_3, v_4\}$ be the two partitions of vertex set of $K_{2,2}$. Then \mathcal{A} consists of 4 distinct path homotopy classes

$\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3$ and \mathcal{P}_4 , corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_2, v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3, v_2\}$ and $\{v_1, v_4, v_2\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 8$. Clearly h is injective $K_{2,2}$ is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Second, consider complete bipartite graph $K_{2,3}$. Let $A = \{v_1, v_2\}$ and $B = \{v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ be the two partitions of vertex set of $K_{2,3}$. Then \mathcal{A} consists of 9 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8$ and \mathcal{P}_9 , corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_2, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_2, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_5, v_1\}, \{v_2, v_4, v_1\}, \{v_4, v_2, v_5\}, \{v_1, v_4, v_5\}$ and $\{v_2, v_3, v_1\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 15$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 10$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 20$, $h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 6$. Clearly h is injective $K_{2,3}$ is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider a complete bipartite graph $K_{2,4}$. In any labelling of the vertices we get as the value of $h(\mathcal{P})$ one of 12, 24 and 30. Since $12 = 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 = 1 \cdot 6 \cdot 2$, $24 = 1 \cdot 6 \cdot 4 = 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 2$ and $30 = 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 5 = 1 \cdot 6 \cdot 5$, we get two distinct path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' with $h(\mathcal{P}) = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence $K_{2,4}$ is not strongly 2-multiplicative. Like this one can show that, a complete bipartite graph $K_{2,n}$, for $n > 4$ is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.16 *The graph $P_2 + P_n$ is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $n \leq 3$.*

Proof First, consider the graph $P_2 + P_2$. This is same as K_4 , which is strongly 2-multiplicative by Theorem 2.11.

Second, consider the graph $P_2 + P_3$. Then \mathcal{A} consists of 10 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \mathcal{P}_5, \mathcal{P}_6, \mathcal{P}_7, \mathcal{P}_8, \mathcal{P}_9$ and \mathcal{P}_{10} corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_2, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_2, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_5, v_1\}, \{v_2, v_4, v_1\}, \{v_4, v_2, v_5\}, \{v_1, v_4, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_3, v_1\}$ and $\{v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 15$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 10$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 20$, $h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 60$. Clearly h is injective and $P_2 + P_3$ is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider graph $P_2 + P_n$ where $n \geq 4$. In any labeling of the vertices we can find two path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' such that $\mathcal{P} \neq \mathcal{P}'$ but $h(\mathcal{P}) = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence for $n \geq 4$, $P_2 + P_n$ is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.17 *The peterson graph is strongly 2-multiplicative.*

Proof Consider a peterson graph with vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, \dots, v_{10}$.

Figure 5

Then \mathcal{A} consists of 21 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_{21}$, corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_4, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_5, v_2, v_4\}, \{v_5, v_3, v_1\}, \{v_1, v_4, v_2\}, \{v_2, v_5, v_3\}, \{v_6, v_7, v_8\}, \{v_7, v_8, v_9\}, \{v_8, v_9, v_{10}\}, \{v_9, v_{10}, v_6\}, \{v_9, v_{10}, v_4\}, \{v_{10}, v_6, v_7\}, \{v_6, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_6, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_7, v_2, v_5\}, \{v_7, v_2, v_3\}, \{v_8, v_3, v_1\}, \{v_8, v_3, v_5\}, \{v_9, v_4, v_2\}, \{v_9, v_4, v_1\}, \{v_{10}, v_5, v_3\}$ and $\{v_{10}, v_5, v_2\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_i = i$, for $1 \leq i \leq 7$, $v_8 = 9$, $v_9 = 8$, $v_{10} = 10$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 15$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 378$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 504$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 720$, $h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 480$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 320$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 420$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 18$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{14}) = 70$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{15}) = 42$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{16}) = 27$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{17}) = 135$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{18}) = 64$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{19}) = 32$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{20}) = 150$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{21}) = 100$. Clearly h is injective peterson graph is strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

Theorem 2.18 *The windmill K_n^m is strongly 2-multiplicative if and only if $m \leq 3, n \leq 3$.*

Proof First, if $m = 2$, then the proof follows from the proof of Theorem 2.5, with $n = 3$.

Second, consider the K_3^3 with vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6$ and v_7 such that v_1 be the common vertex as shown in the figure.

Figure 6

Then \mathcal{A} consists of 15 distinct path homotopy classes $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4, \dots, \mathcal{P}_{15}$ corresponding to paths having vertex sets $\{v_2, v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_2, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_3, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_5\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_4, v_1, v_7\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_6\}, \{v_5, v_1, v_7\}$ and $\{v_6, v_1, v_7\}$ respectively. We label the vertices as follows: $v_1 = 2$, $v_2 = 1$ and $v_i = i$ for all i for $3 \leq i \leq 7$. Then $h(\mathcal{P}_1) = 6$, $h(\mathcal{P}_2) = 8$, $h(\mathcal{P}_3) = 10$, $h(\mathcal{P}_4) = 12$, $h(\mathcal{P}_5) = 14$, $h(\mathcal{P}_6) = 24$, $h(\mathcal{P}_7) = 30$, $h(\mathcal{P}_8) = 36$, $h(\mathcal{P}_9) = 42$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{10}) = 40$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{11}) = 48$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{12}) = 56$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{13}) = 60$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{14}) = 70$, $h(\mathcal{P}_{15}) = 84$. Clearly h is injective K_3^3 is strongly 2-multiplicative.

Finally, consider a windmill K_n^m for $m \geq 3, n > 3$. In any labelling of the vertices, we can find two path homotopy classes \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' such that $\mathcal{P} \neq \mathcal{P}'$, but $h(\mathcal{P}) = h(\mathcal{P}')$. Hence for $n \geq 3, m \geq 3$, K_n^m is not strongly 2-multiplicative. \square

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